

NFDI 4
BIODIVERSITY
BIODIVERSITY, ECOLOGY & ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

NFDI4Biodiversity - National and international involvement

First strategic report

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Impressum

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Content

Executive Summary	2
1 Background	2
2 Method	3
3 Results	4
3.1 The Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF	4
3.2 Bundesamt für Naturschutz - BfN.....	4
3.3 Research Data Alliance - RDA	4
3.4 European Open Science Cloud - EOSC.....	4
3.5 Bioschemas - Bioschemas.org.....	5
3.6 Atlas of Living Australia - ALA.....	5
3.7 German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure - de.NBI	5
3.8 BMBF-Forschungsinitiative zum Erhalt der Artenvielfalt - FEdA	5
3.9 Deutsches Zentrum für integrative Biodiversitätsforschung - iDiv	6
3.10 Biodiversity Information Standards - TDWG	6
4 Assessment of current involvement	6
5 Outlook	7
6 References	8

Executive Summary

The success of developing the NFDI4Biodiversity infrastructure will depend critically on technical and organizational interaction with the evolving national and international landscape of data infrastructures. However, given the large number of relevant stakeholders, priorities need to be identified and given special attention in the first phase of the project. Based on the existing activities of the consortium members as well as a consultation process of the NFDI4Biodiversity Special Interest Group "Strategy", the following initiatives and infrastructures have been identified as priorities:

- The Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF
- Bundesamt für Naturschutz - BfN
- Research Data Alliance - RDA
- European Open Science Cloud - EOSC
- Bioschemas - Bioschemas.org
- Atlas of Living Australia - ALA
- German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure - de.NBI
- BMBF-Forschungsinitiative zum Erhalt der Artenvielfalt - FEdA
- Deutsches Zentrum für integrative Biodiversitätsforschung - iDiv
- Biodiversity Information Standards - TDWG

With the exception of bioschemas.org and EOSC, future collaborations can build on existing consortium contacts and activities. In the next step, concrete measures for cooperation with the various initiatives will now be coordinated and started.

1 Background

NFDI4Biodiversity is born into a complex and rapidly evolving landscape of existing biodiversity data initiatives, projects, and infrastructures. At national, European, and international level, these are concerned, among other things, with the organisation of communities, the standardization of data processes, and the development of concrete infrastructure components and services that are used in a wide range of research activities.

Members of the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium are already highly networked with existing initiatives and infrastructures. In addition to the many memberships in the relevant community associations, this includes active participation in working groups and, in many cases, their coordination.

For NFDI4Biodiversity it will be important to identify initiatives with high importance for the own infrastructure development and to strategically strengthen the respective cooperation. Cooperations can refer, for example, to the joint specification of standards, the development of software components, and the mutual use of data and services.

In the past, there have been numerous attempts, usually in the context of infrastructure projects, to present landscape analyses, e.g. for the fields of biodiversity informatics and eco-informatics. Examples include the overview of biodiversity informatics infrastructures produced as part of the EUBON project (Bingham et al. 2017) as well as the overview of biodiversity-related data standards produced as part of LifeWatch (Hernandez-Ernst et al. 2010).

As part of the work planning for task area 2 of the NFDI4Biodiversity project, it was decided that a further landscape analysis should not be carried out, as this would involve a great deal of effort and would be difficult to keep up to date in view of the rapidly changing context. Instead, a more focused approach was taken, building on the strategic alliances already identified through the NFDI4Biodiversity proposal development process and looking only at potentially relevant partnerships.

This report provides a list of initiatives that were assessed as priorities for collaborations at this time (after the first year of the project). This assessment and the underlying data are not considered finalised and will be continuously developed as the project progresses.

2 Method

To create an overview of potential strategic partnerships, as well as their prioritization, we first extracted the initiatives and infrastructures already mentioned in the NFDI4Biodiversity proposal and documented them consistently in an online spreadsheet (Fig. 1). The overview includes a brief description of each initiative as well as contact persons and existing contacts in the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium (if available). The table was then completed by the consortium partners with missing entries. As a result, 59 initiatives of particular relevance to NFDI4Biodiversity are now listed.

Subsequently, in preparation for a discussion in the "SIG Strategy" group (Glöckner, Bonn, Güntsch, König-Ries, Felden, Diepenbroek, Overmann), a further classification of the respective initiatives was made according to various criteria (information only, liaison, co-operation, use-case, national, international).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Organization/ Network	Full Name	I	L	K	U	Na	In	Focus	Representativ Contact perso
2	ALA Community	An open community created around the Atlas of Living Australia platform.			x			x	sollten wir die ALA Funktionalitäten nutzen Open Source Community	
3	Alliance for Biodiversity Knowledge							x	align efforts to deliver current, accurate and comprehensive data, information and knowledge on the world's biodiversity	
4	ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons	x					x	Collaboration on selected topics can be profitable The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) is a transformational initiative that enables Australian research community and industry access to nationally significant, leading edge data intensive eInfrastructure, platforms, skills and collections of high-quality data.	Andrew Treloar
5	BfN - NMZB	Bundesamt für Naturschutz / Nationales Monitoringzentrum zur Biodiversität		x		x	x		Interfaces and interoperability between infrastructures	Andreas Krüss (
6	BiodiFAIRse (GOFAIR)	The BiodiFAIRse GO FAIR Implementation Network	x					x	Active GO FAIR Implementation Network aus Frankreich, Data and metadata portals: develop metadata and data portals based on FAIR utilities linked to PIDs and open licences, using the expertise already developed around the "Living Atlases" community (https://living-atlases.gbif.org/)	Anne-Sophie Archambeau archambeau@g Yvan le Bras yvan.le-bras@m
7	Biodiversity Heritage Library (BHL)		x					x	Open access digital library for biodiversity literature and archives	
8	Bioportal			x	x			x	Biomedical Ontologies	
9	Bioscan	BIOSCAN Europe							Initiative centered around methodology (metabarcoding) Part of the International Barcode of Life Consortium (IBOL) and its global BIOSCAN initiative. Aim is to establish a European hub for the International Barcode of Life consortium.	
10	BMU, Unterabteilung NI (Naturschutz)			x	(x)		x		Nature Conservation	Josef Tumberine Antonia Ortmar
11	BUND	Bund für Umwelt und Naturschutz Deutschland		x	(x)		x		Umweltverband (praktischer Naturschutz), Citizen Science. Der BUND finanziert sich überwiegend aus seinen eigenen Einnahmen – primär durch Mitgliedsbeiträge und Spenden. Der BUND ist ein von Politik und Wirtschaft unabhängiger Verband.	Magnus Wessel
12	Bürger schaffen Wissen		x				x		Citizen Science (vorwiegend MN und WID); für Aufbau und Mobilisierung von Daten sind eher Fachgesellschaften, NABU, BUND und Konferenz der Arten (Museum König) et al wichtig; diese sind anders organisiert, daneben gibt es noch Senckenberg, Museum König und Uni CS Centren, CS&Helmholtz & Fraunhofer CS Netzwerk	Susanne Hecker
13	CETAF	Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities			x			x	Collections and Research facilities, Standards & workflows -> Interoperability, Workinggroups as Digitization and e-learning/Training; SIG European Biodiversity Monitoring Group -	Michelle Price (Chair), Ana Cas (General Secret

Fig. 1: Part of the matrix for the identification of strategic partnerships.

On the basis of the data thus available, a further prioritization was carried out within the framework of the SIG strategy, in which the members could each name up to 10 initiatives with, in their view, outstanding significance for NFDI4Biodiversity.

3 Results

As a result of the prioritization process described in the last section, the following 10 initiatives and infrastructures are considered to be of particular importance for collaborations (short descriptions taken from the respective websites):

3.1 The Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF

<http://www.gbif.org>

GBIF—the Global Biodiversity Information Facility—is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.

3.2 Bundesamt für Naturschutz - BfN

<https://www.bfn.de>

The German Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (Bundesamt für Naturschutz – BfN) is the German government's scientific authority with responsibility for national and international nature conservation. BfN is one of the government's departmental research agencies and reports to the German Environment Ministry (BMUB). As of January 2021, the BfN has been tasked with the hosting of the National Monitoring Center on Biodiversity in Germany (Nationales Monitoringzentrum zur Biodiversität, NMZB; www.monitoringzentrum.de). The NMZB is to develop an overarching overall concept for nationwide biodiversity monitoring in cooperation with all stakeholders, taking into account the requirements of European and international biodiversity reporting.

3.3 Research Data Alliance - RDA

<https://www.rd-alliance.org>

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 by the European Commission, the United States Government's National Science Foundation and National Institute of Standards and Technology, and the Australian Government's Department of Innovation with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data.

3.4 European Open Science Cloud - EOSC

<https://eosc-portal.eu/>

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative will offer researchers a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis, and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines by federating existing data infrastructures.

EOSC is being co-created in a series of funded projects and initiatives from Member States and Associated Countries. The EOSC Association, funded in 2020, governs the future development of the EOSC through a European Partnership

under Horizon Europe, the European Commission's Research Framework Programme.

3.5 Bioschemas - Bioschemas.org

<https://bioschemas.org/>

Bioschemas aims to improve the Findability on the Web of life sciences resources such as datasets, software, and training materials. It does this by encouraging people in the life sciences to use Schema.org markup in their websites so that they are indexable by search engines and other services. Bioschemas encourages the consistent use of markup to ease the consumption of the contained markup across many sites.

3.6 Atlas of Living Australia - ALA

<https://living-atlases.gbif.org/>

The Atlas of Living Australia (ALA) is a collaborative, digital, open infrastructure that pulls together Australian biodiversity data from multiple sources, making it accessible and reusable for scientists, policymakers, environmental planners, and land managers, industry and the general public. The ALA Open Source Framework is publicly available and has attracted a community of developers who deploy the portal for living atlases around the world.

3.7 German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure - de.NBI

<https://www.denbi.de/>

The 'German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure – de.NBI' is a national, academic, and non-profit infrastructure supported by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research providing bioinformatics services to users in life sciences research and biomedicine in Germany and Europe. The partners organize training events, courses, and summer schools on tools, standards, and computing services provided by de.NBI to assist researchers to more effectively exploit their data. de.NBI is the official national node for the European Research Infrastructure ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/>).

3.8 BMBF-Forschungsinitiative zum Erhalt der Artenvielfalt - FEEdA

<https://www.feda.bio>

With the Research Initiative for the Conservation of Biodiversity (FEEdA), the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) has implemented a ten-year programme to support biodiversity research and the development of new, effective species conservation measures. The initiative will include up to 40 research projects at various scientific institutions in Germany. The central coordination office is located at the Senckenberg Research Institute in Frankfurt.

The research initiative not only addresses research institutions, but also invites stakeholders from politics, industry, agriculture, and conservation to participate in the dialogue. A central information portal is planned that will also guide to research data acquired and analysed in the course of the programme.

3.9 Deutsches Zentrum für integrative Biodiversitätsforschung - iDiv

<https://www.idiv.de>

iDiv is a research center funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) with more than 400 employees and members based primarily in Halle, Jena and Leipzig. It hosts researchers from more than 35 nations as well as extensive data collections on biodiversity.

3.10 Biodiversity Information Standards - TDWG

<https://www.tdwg.org/>

Historically known as the Taxonomic Databases Working Group, today's Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) is a not-for-profit, scientific and educational association formed to establish international collaboration among the creators, managers and users of biodiversity information and to promote the wider and more effective dissemination and sharing of knowledge about the world's heritage of biological organisms.

4 Assessment of current involvement

For almost all prioritized initiatives, contact persons could be identified in the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium who can act as "ambassadors" through existing activities.

Some have long-standing connections, as in the case of GBIF, TDWG, iDiv, and de.NBI. Relevant German GBIF node representatives are also active both in GFBio and NFDI4Biodiversity. The same holds true for the de.NBI Service Centers and de.NBI Cloud providers and the iDiv Research Center. Alignments in terms of cooperation and development can therefore be built on existing relations.

From TDWG, a letter of support was obtained during the NFDI4Biodiversity proposal stage and the current chair, Deborah Paul, was appointed as a member of the Strategic Advisory Board. NFDI4Biodiversity members have previously been engaged in TDWG and RDA working groups and will continue to do so. In TDWG, for example, Anton Güntsch (BGBM) co-leads the Interest Groups for "ABCD" and "Biodiversity Services and Clients". Mareike Petersen (MfN) is Chair of the "Outreach and Communication" subcommittee.

In the case of the new national initiatives FEdA and NMZB (BfN), which were funded in parallel to the NFDI, actions have been taken to establish relations. The founding manager of the National Monitoring Centre NMZB has accepted a position as a member of the NFDI4Biodiversity Strategic Advisory Board. The consortium speaker Frank Oliver Glöckner was appointed as a member of the main NMZB Expert Panel ("Fachgremium für Grundsatzfragen").

Connections to the Living Atlas Community (ALA) have been established by the Data and Software Solutions Team of NFDI4Biodiversity, in the course of setting up a test installation of the ALA Open Source Framework.

In the case of bioschema.org and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), appropriate links may still need to be established.

5 Outlook

Building on the results of the first prioritization phase, we will now flesh out the strategies for the various collaborations. The specific activities are diverse and range from a coordinated approach to membership in relevant committees and working groups to the use of software and services (e.g. ALA and GBIF) to collaboration on standards (e.g. TDWG and Bioschemas.org) to the structuring and coordination of service portfolios (e.g. EOSC, de.NBI).

The aim is to avoid the implementation of parallel structures and build the portfolio of NFDI4Biodiversity services with regard to existing offerings (see work programme for Task Area 2, Measure 2). The individual measures will be calibrated based on the NFDI4Biodiversity use cases as well as requirements from technical task areas 3 and 4.

6 References

Bingham H., Doudin M., Weatherdon L., Despot-Belmonte K., Wetzel F., Groom Q., Lewis E., Regan E., Appeltans W., Güntsch A., Mergen P., Agosti D., Penev L., Hoffmann A., Saarenmaa H., Geller G., Kim K., Kim H., Archambeau A., Häuser C., Schmeller D., Geijzendorffer I., García Camacho A., Guerra C., Robertson T., Runnel V., Valland N., Martin C. 2017: The Biodiversity Informatics Landscape: Elements, Connections and Opportunities. Research Ideas and Outcomes 3: e14059.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.3.e14059>

Hernandez-Ernst V, Poigné A, Giddy J, Hardisty A 2010: Data & Modelling Tool Structures - Reference Model. LifeWatch e-science and technology infrastructure for biodiversity data and observatories. Deliverable report 5.1.3.

<https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/56502/1/D5.1.3-ReferenceModel-v1.0.pdf>